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Knowledge and awareness about polycystic ovarian syndrome among females in Western India -A cross sectional survey

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Abstract

Background: Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a common endocrine disorder with prevalence rate range from 5-20% among women of reproductive age in India. Assessing awareness and knowledge regarding PCOS is essential for early diagnosis and management.

Methodology: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 275 female participants using a structured questionnaire. Data regarding demographic characteristics, menstrual history, and knowledge about PCOS symptoms, risk factors, complications, treatment approaches, and awareness regarding screening practices were collected and analyzed descriptively. Result: Most participants were aged 18–24 years (76%), from rural areas (65.4%), unmarried (74.5%), and students (68%). Overall, 82.2% participants had heard about PCOS, and 70.2% were aware of its signs and symptoms. Irregular menstruation (78.5%) was the most recognized symptom, while hormonal imbalance (64%) and weight gain (56.7%) were commonly identified risk factors. Knowledge regarding complications was reported by 65.5% participants, with pregnancy-related complications being the most recognized. Awareness regarding treatment options was observed in 64.7% participants, with medication, healthy diet, exercise, and weight management frequently identified as management strategies. Although 69.8% considered PCOS a public health concern, embarrassment discussing PCOS socially was reported by 64.4% participants. Fear of diagnosis, cultural beliefs, and shyness were major barriers to screening. Conclusion: Awareness regarding PCOS among young women was generally satisfactory. However, gaps remain regarding complications and screening practices. Educational interventions and culturally sensitive awareness programs are needed to promote early diagnosis and effective management of PCOS.

Keywords: PCOS, knowledge, awareness, infertility, hirsutism.

Introduction

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most common endocrine and metabolic disorders affecting women of reproductive age, with an estimated global prevalence ranging from 10–13% of reproductive-aged women.¹ PCOS is a multifactorial disorder characterized by reproductive, metabolic, and psychological manifestations. The major clinical features include hyperandrogenism, irregular or absent menstrual cycles, and polycystic ovaries, which may lead to symptoms such as acne, excessive hair on the face or body, female-pattern

baldness, infertility, delayed pregnancy, stress, and anxiety.¹

PCOS is strongly associated with insulin resistance and metabolic abnormalities, thereby increasing the risk of obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, and other long-term health complications.² Women with PCOS frequently experience infertility due to anovulation or irregular ovulation. Although the exact etiology of PCOS remains unclear, genetic predisposition, hormonal imbalance, sedentary lifestyle, unhealthy dietary habits, and environmental factors are considered important contributors to its development.³

Early diagnosis and appropriate management of PCOS are essential to prevent reproductive and metabolic complications. Diagnosis is guided by the Rotterdam criteria, which include oligo-anovulation, hyperandrogenism, and polycystic ovarian morphology, with Anti-Müllerian hormone serving as an indicator of ovarian morphology. Management of PCOS requires a multifaceted approach that includes lifestyle modifications, weight reduction strategies, dietary changes, and pharmacological interventions. Lifestyle interventions such as regular exercise, dietary management, and behavioral strategies have shown significant potential in improving the metabolic health of patients with PCOS.⁴ Pharmacological therapy and gynecological consultation are also important components of treatment.⁵

Several studies have reported inadequate awareness and limited knowledge regarding PCOS among young women, particularly concerning its symptoms, risk factors, complications, and lifestyle modifications.⁶⁻⁸ Delayed diagnosis and poor awareness may contribute to worsening reproductive, metabolic, and psychological outcomes. Furthermore, the prevalence of PCOS and associated symptoms has been increasing in recent years without a proportional rise in awareness levels among females.⁹ Increasing awareness regarding PCOS through health education and community-based interventions is therefore essential for promoting early detection, timely treatment, and prevention of long-term complications. In India, the burden of PCOS has increased considerably in recent years, largely due to changing lifestyles, physical inactivity, unhealthy dietary patterns, and lack of awareness. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to assess the prevalence of PCOS and evaluate the knowledge and awareness regarding PCOS among females.

Methodology

A population-based cross-sectional interview survey was conducted between February and April 2025 among women of reproductive age (18–40 years). A structured, validated, self-administered questionnaire was developed using Google Forms following an extensive literature review. Content validity was established by subject experts, and pilot testing was performed on a small cohort of female students to assess clarity and reliability. Data were collected through interviews using the finalized Google Form after obtaining verbal informed consent. The questionnaire comprised three sections: demographic characteristics (10 items), knowledge regarding PCOS (13 items), and awareness regarding PCOS (10 items). Data were analyzed using Microsoft

Excel, and descriptive statistics were expressed as frequencies and percentages

Results

The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1. Among the 275 participants, the majority belonged to the 18–24 years age group (76%), were from rural areas (65.4%), and unmarried (74.5%). Most participants were students (68%), and 52.4% had post-secondary education. Regarding menstrual characteristics, 74.9% reported regular menstrual cycles, while 25.1% experienced irregular menstruation. A menstrual duration of 3–5 days was reported by 64% participants. Abnormal body hair growth was observed in 14.5% participants. Based on BMI classification, 15.3% were overweight, whereas 84.7% had normal BMI. Hypertension (16.8%) and diabetes (16.4%) were the most frequently reported comorbidities, followed by hyperthyroidism (13.5%) and obesity (11.3%).

The knowledge-related findings are summarized in Table 2. Overall, 82.2% participants had heard about polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Major information sources included friends (44.4%), doctors (39.6%), and the internet (38.8%). PCOS was self-reported by 28.4% participants, while 19.3% reported a family history of the disorder. Knowledge regarding PCOS signs and symptoms was observed in 70.2% participants. Irregular or absent menstruation (78.5%) was the most commonly recognized symptom, followed by abnormal hair growth (45.2%), acne/rashes (45.2%), stress (43%), anxiety (34.1%), and infertility (31.1%). Awareness regarding PCOS risk factors was reported by 69.1% participants, with hormonal imbalance (64%) and weight gain (56.7%) being the most frequently identified factors, followed by genetics (41.5%), junk food consumption (34.2%), and physical inactivity (33.1%). Knowledge regarding PCOS complications was present in 65.5% participants. Pregnancy-related complications (60.4%) were the most commonly identified, followed by anxiety (39.3%), hypertension (38.9%), depression (36%), and diabetes (30.9%). Regarding diagnostic methods, symptom-based diagnosis (53%) and hormone testing (52.6%) were more frequently recognized than ultrasonography (42.2%) and laparoscopy (15.3%). Awareness regarding treatment approaches was reported by 64.7% participants, with medication (67.3%), healthy diet (65%), exercise (57.9%), and weight management (51.5%) being the most commonly identified management strategies.

Table 1. Demographic data of the study participants.

Variables	Frequency (n=275)	Percentage (%)	Variables	Frequency (n=275)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (Years)			Comorbidity		
18–24	209	76.0	Diabetes	45	16.4
25–30	39	14.2	Hypertension	46	16.8
31–40	27	9.8	Hyperthyroidism	37	13.5
			Obesity	31	11.3
			Other	7	2.6
Education			Menstrual Period		
SSC	19	6.9	Regular	206	74.9
HSC	112	40.7	Irregular	69	25.1
Graduate	119	43.3			
Post-graduate	25	9.1			
Marital Status			Menstrual Period Duration		
Married	70	25.5	<2 days	33	12.0
Unmarried	205	74.5	3–5 days	176	64.0
			>5 days	66	24.0
Occupation			Body Hair Growth		
Student	187	68.0	Normal	235	85.5
Job workers	51	18.5	Abnormal	40	14.5
House wife	31	11.3			
Others	6	2.2			
Residence			Body Mass Index		
Urban	95	34.6	Normal	233	84.7
Rural	180	65.4	Overweight	42	15.3

Table 2. Knowledge of the study participants towards PCOS.

Variables	Frequency (n=275)	%	Variables	Frequency (n=275)	%
Have you heard about PCOS?			Risk Factors of PCOS		
Yes	226	82.2	Genetics	114	41.5
No	49	17.8	Weight gain	156	56.7
Source of Information			Hormonal imbalance	176	64.0
Friend	122	44.4	Physical inactivity	91	33.1
Doctor	106	39.6	Sedentary lifestyle	79	28.7
Family	64	23.3	Junk food intake	94	34.2
Health Educator	61	22.2	Do you know the complications related to PCOS?		
Internet	104	38.8	Yes	180	65.5
Do you have PCOS?			No	95	34.5
Yes	78	28.4	Complications Associated with PCOS		
No	197	71.6	Diabetes	85	30.9
Anyone in your family have PCOS?			Hypertension	107	38.9
Yes	53	19.3	Asthma	54	19.6
No	222	80.7	Pregnancy complications	166	60.4
Do you know the signs & symptoms of PCOS?			Anxiety	108	39.3
Yes	193	70.2	Depression	99	36.0
No	82	29.8	Diagnosis Test of PCOS		
Signs & Symptoms of PCOS			Based on symptoms	142	53.0
Irregular menstrual periods	216	78.54	Hormones test	141	52.6
Hair growth of body/face	122	45.2	Ultrasonography	113	42.2
Facial acne/Rashes	122	45.2	Laparoscopy	41	15.3
Infertility	84	31.1	Do you know the treatment option of PCOS?		

Delay in pregnancy	66	24.4	Yes	178	64.7
Pelvic pain	65	24.1	No	97	35.3
Stress	116	43.0	Treatment of PCOS		
Anxiety	92	34.1	Medication	179	67.3
Obesity	02	0.7	Weight manage-	137	51.5
Patches on skin	45	16.7	Healthy diet	173	65.0
Other	06	2.2	Exercise	154	57.9
Do you know the risk factors of PCOS?			Ovarian surgery	45	16.9
Yes	190	69.1	Progestin therapy	37	13.9
No	85	30.9			

Table 3. Awareness of participants towards PCOS

Variables	Frequency	%	Variables	Frequency	%
Do you consider PCOS as a public health issue?			Perceptions of Undergoing PCOS Screening		
Yes	192	69.8	I have religious issue in doing so	65	23.6
No	83	30.2	It is culturally unacceptable	62	22.6
Feel embarrassed talking about PCOS in society?			It is expensive	53	19.3
Yes	177	64.4	Only when the need arises	84	30.5
No	98	35.6	Yes, it's better	142	51.6

Your action when your friend reveals PCOS diagnosis			Reason for Undergoing PCOS Screening		
Comfort her	243	88.4	Advice of friend	87	31.6
Shy away from her	32	11.6	Doctor's advice	182	66.2
Attitude of family members regarding PCOS diagnosis			Irregular periods	139	50.5
Supportive	259	94.2	Family members having PCOS	64	23.3
Non-supportive	16	5.8	Fear of having the disease	49	17.8
Attitude of your colleagues on PCOS diagnosis			Media awareness	46	16.7
Supportive	259	94.2	Barriers to Undergoing PCOS Screening		
Non-supportive	16	5.8	Cultural/Tradition	108	39.3
Do you refer PCOS patients for consultation?			Fear of diagnosing disease	137	49.8
Yes	218	79.3	Examined by male	91	33.1
No	57	20.7	Social pressure	75	27.3
Do you ever discuss PCOS disease with doctor?			Shyness	101	36.7
Yes	153	55.6			
No	122	44.4			

The awareness-related findings are presented in Table 3. Overall, 69.8% participants considered PCOS a public health concern, while 64.4% reported embarrassment discussing PCOS socially. Supportive attitudes toward individuals with PCOS were observed, with 88.4% comforting affected friends and 94.2% reporting supportive behavior from family members and colleagues. Most participants (79.3%) indicated they would refer PCOS patients to a gynecologist; however, only 55.6% had discussed PCOS with a healthcare professional. Regarding screening practices, 51.6% perceived PCOS screening at hospitals or clinics as beneficial, whereas religious concerns (23.6%), cultural unacceptability (22.6%), and financial burden (19.3%) were identified as barriers. Doctor's advice (66.2%) and irregular menstruation (50.5%) were the primary motivations for PCOS screening. Fear of disease diagnosis (49.8%) was the most frequently reported screening barrier, followed by cultural or traditional beliefs (39.3%), shyness (36.7%), lack of female doctors or hesitation toward male examination (33.1%), and social pressure (27.3%).

Discussion

The study population mainly consisted of young unmarried students, similar to previous Indian studies conducted among college women and young adults.¹⁰ The predominance of rural participants highlights the importance of improving reproductive health awareness in rural communities. Hypertension, diabetes, obesity, and hyperthyroidism were common comorbidities observed in the present study, which is consistent with previous reports showing strong associations between PCOS and metabolic disorders.^{2,11} About one-fourth of participants reported irregular menstrual cycles, which is a common clinical feature of PCOS associated with hormonal imbalance and ovulatory dysfunction. Similar findings have been reported in earlier studies among young women. The presence of abnormal body hair growth and overweight participants further supports the role of hyperandrogenism and obesity in PCOS development.^{7,8} These findings emphasize the need for early screening, lifestyle modification, and awareness programs to reduce PCOS-related complications among young women

Awareness regarding treatment options was satisfactory, with medication, healthy diet, exercise, and weight management being the most frequently identified approaches. These findings emphasize the importance of lifestyle modification in PCOS management, which is considered a first-line strategy for improving metabolic, reproductive, and psychological outcomes. Recent study have highlighted that dietary modification, physical activity, and behavioral interventions play a crucial role in reducing insulin resistance, promoting weight control, and minimizing long-term complications associated with PCOS.¹³ However, gaps still exist regarding comprehensive understanding of complications and long-term consequences of PCOS, indicating the need for targeted educational and awareness programs.

The present study revealed that most participants considered PCOS a significant public health issue; however, embarrassment and social stigma related to discussing reproductive health conditions were still common. Similar findings have been reported in previous studies where cultural beliefs and social stigma negatively affected PCOS awareness and healthcare-seeking behavior among women.¹⁴ Despite social barriers, participants demonstrated supportive attitudes toward individuals diagnosed with PCOS, indicating improving social acceptance and awareness. Most respondents also preferred gynecological consultation, highlighting positive healthcare-seeking attitudes. Doctor's advice and menstrual irregularities were the major motivating factors for PCOS screening,

which is consistent with earlier studies reporting that symptoms often prompt women to seek medical consultation.¹¹ Fear of diagnosis, cultural beliefs, shyness, and lack of female healthcare professionals were major barriers to screening in the present study. Similar barriers have been identified in previous Indian studies addressing reproductive health services among women.¹⁵ These findings emphasize the need for culturally sensitive awareness programs, accessible screening facilities, and improved counseling services to encourage early diagnosis and management of PCOS.¹⁶

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that awareness and knowledge regarding polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) among young women were generally satisfactory. However, important gaps still exist regarding its risk factors, long-term complications, and screening practices. Social stigma, fear of diagnosis, and cultural barriers continue to influence healthcare-seeking behavior and early diagnosis. The findings highlight the need for targeted educational interventions, culturally sensitive awareness programs, and accessible reproductive healthcare services to promote early detection, effective management, and prevention of PCOS-related complications among women.

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